

Tinnitus and somatic dysfunction: the role of neuromuscular manual therapy

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Abstract

Tinnitus is a growing problem in the general population. It can be classified as objective, a sound generated by the body that is perceived by the ear, and subjective, a sound caused by aberrant cerebral electric activity that emulates that of sounds. Recent studies have shed light on the role that peripheral somatic-sensory information has in the genesis of such aberrant cerebral activity. Physiotherapy, therefore, through manual therapy can play a central role in tinnitus management. In this study, an experimental group A (n = 10) and a control group B (n = 15) were subjected to two different therapies: the group A was subject to 8 sessions of neuromuscular therapy, the group B followed a classical cognitive-behavioral therapy protocol (TRT). The measurement of the results was done using the THI questionnaire. At T1, both groups showed an improvement in the initial situation: Group A, with an average reduction of 7 points on the THI total score (p = 0.0088) and group B with an average reduction of 31.7 points (p = 0.000721). Group A was also given three numerical scales (1-100), relating to some aspects of tinnitus, all significantly reduced: mean volume of tinnitus decreased by 16 points (p = 0.00557); Time percentage with tinnitus, decreased by 24.5 points (p = 0.0124); Time percentage, in which tinnitus was present, with negative feelings and emotions, decreased by 13.5 points (p = 0.030516). We can conclude that neuromuscular manual therapy may have a significant role in the management of subjective tinnitus.

Keywords: : tinnitus, manual therapy, somatic dysfunction, quality of life reduction

Introduction

Tinnitus is, by definition, the presence of a perceived sound from the subject that is not audible by other people, as it is not generated by external sources. It can be manifested in very different forms, described as a whistle, a buzz, a rustle, a pure tone, and so on; Can be perceived in one or both ears, at one or more frequencies, pulsating, waving, continuous or intermittent.

Tinnitus is a problem that is often overlooked by doctors, as it is not easily identifiable, quantifiable and difficult to care for, which is why it is becoming increasingly chronic. In predisposed subjects, it can also lead to depression and suicidal ideas, thus transforming what is a symptom, which is in fact harmless to the individual, in a problem to be addressed seriously in terms of seeking new therapeutic proposals, patients care, information about this condition, prevention, follow-up and multidisciplinary intervention. To this, other alarming data are added: the increase in incidence in the general population and its prevalence. Data from the National Center for Health Statistics, a research center at the American Department of Health, Education and Welfare, indicate that 30% of the general population has got tinnitus and 6% of them (1.8% of the general population) has a devastating

and disabling tinnitus. One of the most important variables for tinnitus prevalence is age. Such epidemiological data emerge from investigations conducted in the United States, the United Kingdom, Sweden and Norway [1].

Recently, the direction of scientific research about the relationship between tinnitus and somatic dysfunction has been updated, which in recent years has revealed the highest level of interrelation between the two systems, the auditory and musculoskeletal system.

The vast majority of patients with tinnitus states that they have the ability to modulate tinnitus with voluntary or passive movements of the jaw, neck, eyes or pressure applied to the regions of the head and neck [2]. In addition, increased prevalence of somatoform disorders was observed in tinnitus individuals [3]. All this has led to the search for the interrelationship between somatic and auditory systems. As widely demonstrated by Shore, Langguth et al. [2], this communication is much more complex than one could think of, involving neurons of both first and second order.

Assons from the ganglia of the roots and the trigeminal nerve project to the ventricular cochlear nucleus (NCV) [4,5]. These small projections may belong to the B system, that consists in small ameliar fibers. The

cells projecting from the semiannual ganglion are located in the medial or ophthalmic portion, and the lateral or mandibular [6]. These small and thin fibers arrive at the lateral and medial margins of the NCV. The projections originated from the dorsal root ganglia are located at the root level C2; Their termination zone corresponds to the NCV media margin [4,5].

Second-order somato-sensory neurons projecting to the cochlear nucleus are located in the nucleus of the descending root of the trigeminal [7,8] and in the dorsal nuclei [7,9-12].

In addition to relationships with the NC, there are several other multisensory pathways that connect structures belonging to the auditory system, such as lower coliculus, to the somato-sensory system; Also the interneurons of these pathways are mainly contained in the descending root of the trigeminal and in the nuclei of the spine [13]. Some of these, even, would be projected at the same time at both the NC and the outer layer of the ICs by collateral axons [14].

Studies on the indigo piglet showed that, as an electric stimulation of the ophthalmic or mandibular branch of the trigeminal nerve, it could evoke NCV responses [15] and inhibit or excite NCD neurons [16,17];

Concentrated experiments on the backbone nuclei were carried out in similar ways: here, NCD responses to electrical stimulation were both excitation and inhibition. In particular, these responses were both short and long-latency inhibitions, as well as an increase, though only transitional, of activity [18].

The non-classical auditory way is also known as an extra lemniscal or diffused way [19]. Although it is represented in the same nuclei of the classical street, it involves different portions of the latter, and it has great ability to interact with other sensory systems.

It is in these portions, in fact, that the somato-sensorial afferents come, correlating with the acoustic ones.

This extra-lemniscal route has been the subject of a study [20], which has shown that a progressive decrease in suicidal sensory involvement in acoustic perception occurs during the growth of the individual; This phenomenon should be interpreted as a physiological process of maturation of the nervous system and its connections. This change is the result of a specialization in which the function of processing inputs is entrusted to a more evolved system such as the classical auditory path, from a phylogenetically oldest structure such as the non-classical pathway. The former can then become active again over the course of life, following a neuroplastic re-elaboration resulting from pathological events such as, for example, acoustic overexposure. There are, globally, two fundamental differences regarding the relationships between

both the auditory pathways between the thalamus and the upper structures: the first is the bypass of the primary auditory cortex that the ascending fibers of the non-classical path perform, excluding that area, from the elaboration of stimuli; The second is the direct connection, which the other talam-bearing fibers allow, with the limbic system, which, as illustrated in the following section, plays a central role both in genesis and in tinnitus maintenance.

The constant perception of an abnormal sound is, in some cases, anxiety and depression, as well as phonophobia, or a state of uneasiness and stress that is manifested by exposure to sounds of a modest intensity. These pathologies can, in turn, act as perpetuating agents of tinnitus, causing both the attention paid to it over the course of the day, and a real increase in the perceived intensity of subjects. There is no certainty about post-traumatic stress disorder (DPTS) [21], but a condition of mere stress seems to affect the level of perception of tinnitus in those who are already affected, and appears to be directly involved in its etiopathogenesis[22]. Mood noise disorders are generally due to a mechanism established in the limbic system, a complex control system consisting of subcortical, phylogenetically archaic structures, and cerebral cortex portions. It is therefore important to analyze the relationship between the auditory system and the limbic system. Information from the non-classical route bypasses the primary auditory cortex and subsequent multisensory integrative areas, reaching directly to the amygdala lateral nucleus [19]. It should be remembered that this structure is directly involved in the states of anxiety, stress, and mood-tone disorders. If the bark is excluded from such communication, the non-classical route may be associated with more or less serious mood disorders, often associated with tinnitus.

Travell and Simons have defined the trigger point (TP) as "A hyper-irritable portion of a skeletal muscle to which is associated a palpable nodule that is painful at the touch. At pressure, this point may evoke pain, motor dysfunction and autonomic phenomena in specific districts for each trigger point " [23]. To date, the theories about the genesis of such trigger points are numerous and in some cases still unclear, but it is still possible to identify some fixed points.

In general, certain causes of TP are known: muscular overload, lack of exercise, repeated microtraumas, functional overload, trauma and psychological stress, sleep disturbances, vitamin deficiencies, joint problems, stress, chronic muscular contraction [24]. TPs give rise to a wide range of symptoms such as local and reported pain, ROM reduction, movement pain, motor dysfunction, muscular weakness, altered muscle recruitment, myotensive

headache, temporomandibular joint disorders, postural alterations and, As we will see, tinnitus.

The sensitive component is of particular interest. TPs are, in fact, painful; This feeling is carried by fibers A- δ and C. Different stimuli stimulate nociceptive transmission, such as mechanical pressure, thermal stimuli, but also endogenous elements such as K⁺ ions, protons, free radicals, and a lack of ATP. Many substances, both to promote and to inhibit nociceptive transmission, are involved in such mechanisms; In general, an increase in sensitivity to these molecules was assumed following chronicization of the contractile state of a given muscle band [25]. A persistent nociceptive transmission by the TP may result in a defined phenomenon of central excitation, that is an expression of neuroplasticity that results in morpho-functional changes in the posterior horn of the gray bone marrow substance. In this way it becomes a kind of lens where nociceptive signals coming from other parts of the body, including somatic and visceral dysfunctions, converge and amplify and their origin is delocalized. In this way, the postsynaptic interneurons will have a lower activation threshold, a greater input response and an increase in their receptive range. They will depolarize with greater frequency, even spontaneously, so that the nociceptive impulses coming to the thalamus and the cerebral cortex will give rise to the phenomena described above. This phenomenon is known as convergence theory. Central excitement, influencing the descending inhibitory system, can also lead to phenomena such as allodynia and hyperopathy, pathologies that affect the perception of pain.

The autonomic component of TPs could also play a crucial role in influencing the auditory system and, therefore, in tinnitus. This activity manifests itself in some with localized sweating, vasoconstriction or vasodilation and pilomotor activity. TPs located on the neck and head may cause tearing and increased nasal secretions [25]. Autonomic Nervous System(ANS) is mainly involved in reflexive arcs, control of cardiac muscle and smooth blood vessels, glands, visceral organs. However, it has also been highlighted in genesis of TP and musculoskeletal dysfunction. Sympathetic neurons that nourish the muscle tissue vessels may end up converging towards the surrounding intrafusal fibers. The local release of norepinephrine may interfere with adrenergic receptors, which are involved in feedback on muscle length, and contributing to the "ATP energy crisis" [25]. Beyond such mechanisms, the ANS may indirectly exacerbate the formation and maintenance of TP through viscerosomatic reflexes. Chronicized transmission from a dysfunctional bowel may activate the central excitation of the dorsal horn, facilitating the segmental transmission of the spinal cord.

All of this can still result in the emergence of feed-back circuits that escalate in increased nociceptive, proprioceptive and intercapital transmission, as well as in the involvement of somatic motor efferent fibers, through the reflex arcing system present at both the medullary and Level of the spinal cord of the V skull nerve.

In conclusion Myofascial dysfunction is able to induce the activation of CNS neuroplasticity by modifying morpho-functional interneuronal receptive fields in the posterior horn of the marrow or at the level of the caudal nucleus of the trigeminal. Such activation can be a consequence of constant and repeating somato-visceral painful stimuli over time. Morphological reorganization, as well as facilitating sensitive inputs, also ends up conditioning the centers of higher integration until reaching the thalamus; Depolarization will then be summoned with minimal stimulation, since all neurons will soon be below the activation threshold. The situation that will therefore be determined following this global reprogramming of the CNS will be an increased transmission of grievances, which will become, thus, aberrant and repeated. Such mechanisms, are then, in the long run, also capable of altering the functioning of other structures, such as the pericytic reddish substance, forming part of the descending inhibitory system

In addition to generating a condition of postural alteration, muscular pain and autonomic and visceral dysfunctions, the establishment of these mechanisms will therefore affect the neuronal populations of the cochlear nuclei, the lower coliculus of the medial genic bodies: the increased transmission of afferent becomes a participant in coding and perceiving sounds.

We have thus come to justify the physiotherapy treatment of myopathic dysfunctions in tinnitus subjects, since the resolution of the pathological or parapsychological situations of the musculoskeletal apparatus will result in an afferent rebalancing, by disabling the facilitated paths and the reflex arcs established, bringing, therefore, a reduction of aberrant inputs, including those that altered the natural homeostasis of the auditory nerve centers.

Materials and methods

This experimental study and the research protocol is compatible with the Declaration of Helsinki. and all subjects involved in the study have been informed about the procedure and the aim of the research and signed the informed consent.

A key aspect in structuring clinical trials on tinnitus is the determination of appropriate criteria for stratification or classification of patients. Given the extreme difference in etiology and comorbidities of this disorder, it will obviously have to be compared with ex-

treme heterogeneity of patients. What emerges from the literature is that there is always extreme variability in treatment outcomes, probably due to the fact that different types of tinnitus are included in the same study groups. Somatic tinnitus is a subgroup of subjective tinnitus, so the aim of the selection of the study group is to first recruit only cases of subjective tinnitus, and then to select and locate subjects with at least a modulation of the tinnitus parameters with the contraction of the head and neck muscles.

The inclusion criteria according to which subjects will be selected as eligible to undertake this rehabilitation path are:

- Adult age
- Tinnitus diagnosis
- Absence of severe hypoacusis
- Cervicalgia and associated headaches
- Negative diagnosis for vestibule-cochlear origin disorders

Serious hypoacusis are conditions in which there is a significant hearing loss, but it must be related to the age of the subject and to the average audiometric condition of subjects in the age group to which it belongs. The presence of cervicalgias or associated headaches testifies to the presence of a somatic dysfunction occurring in the subject, an element that is therefore indispensable as a criterion, as it makes the myofascial system potentially able to determine the perception of a tinnitus. Obviously, subjects included in the study should not exhibit any of the pathologies of the vestibule-cochlear system, which would refer for therapeutic implementation to the specialist in the field.

The exclusion criteria adopted were the following:

- Major low back pain
- Internal pathologies
- Oncologic pathologies
- Rheumatic diseases
- Infectious diseases
- Any other systemic pathology not mentioned above
- Negativity to the "Somatic Test"

It is important to exclude from the treatment subjects who have a significant pathology, which is not due to the spectrum of tinnitus associated pathologies (psychiatric disorders, hyperacusis, phonophobia). Even a major problem of the spine, in fact, would shift the attention to very distant musculoskeletal structures and in any case the therapeutic goal would be altered. In a study by Levine et al [19], a few years ago, the authors proposed to the subjects examined in their trials a test battery that not only showed a comparison of muscular dysfunction in tinnitus perception but also addressed the treatment to structures that had more than once produced a modifica-

tion of the tinnitus pattern. So, that test battery consists in studying free active mandibular movements, specific and selective isometric contractions in the head and neck movements, and a pressure applied at the insertion level of cervical muscles. This survey was called somatic test [26].

The clinical trial was structured with the composition of two study groups. The controlled clinical trial, conducted at the University Centre of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine, "Gabriele D'Annunzio" University in Chieti, provided a manual therapeutic protocol for myopathic dysfunction structures, which was performed over four weeks, with bi-weekly sessions. A second (control) group has performed the most classical psycho-behavioral therapies and perceptual-hearing re-education, psycho-fonctional, or TRT (tinnitus retraining therapy) therapy.

The experimental group, named (A), composed of 10 subjects, was subjected to a total of 8 sessions, lasting about half an hour at the Chair of Physics and Rehabilitation at the University of Chieti-Pescara "G. D'Annunzio". The control group (B), composed of 15 subjects, followed the therapeutic route, but it had an indefinite duration, which was in fact determined by the subject's response to the therapy. The duration of each session was approximately one hour, for a weekly meeting, at the Otorhinolaryngology Department of the "Holy Spirit" Public Hospital in Pescara.

Preliminary examinations to which patients were subjected prior to the onset of therapy were liminary tonal audiometry, with the aim of seeking the auditory threshold for pure tones, investigating the subjective ability of the patient; Tinnitus Pitch, Audiophysical impedance and acoustic oto-reflections reflect the end of cochlear function mainly related to the activity and function of amplification of external ciliary cells. As mentioned above, it is important to attest that there is an influence of any kind on tinnitus, from the musculoskeletal structures, at least in the districts under consideration, which are the head and the neck.

The quantitative analysis method remains the best available tool [27] to quantify intensity, emotional stress, and the reduction of the quality of life of patients. A T0 time assessment was performed by administering questionnaires (THI, TSHCQ) evaluating the perception of tinnitus and the emotional impact it caused to the patient. The same questionnaires were used to evaluate the outcome at T1 time.

The THI is a questionnaire composed of 25 items. The maximum score is 100 points, the minimum is 0. The greater the final result, the greater will be the severity of tinnitus, measured not so much as the perceived intensity, but considering the overall perception of dis-

ability that it determines. In scientific literature it is the most trusted and widespread questionnaire, as it is available in multiple languages.

In 2006, the "Tinnitus Research Initiative" was held, a meeting between the leading scientists in the field of tinned tissues research in Regensburg, Germany, where workshops were organized to develop authoritative and accredited guidelines, both in terms of taking charge and in measuring the therapeutic outcome of tinnitus. What emerged were the guidelines that guarantee credibility, scientific validity and reproducibility to all subsequent publications [28]. The main objective of this meeting was also to structure a reliable and unique Case History for all future clinical trials on tinnitus. A list of items that could be included in an ideal questionnaire prototype was also drawn up; Based on participants' feedback, what emerged is a set of 35 items, of which 14 are considered essential and 21 are highly recommended: the Tinnitus Sample Case History Questionnaire, or TSCHQ. We have identified 3 items consisting of numeric scales, which were used to evaluate the outcome of our treatments:

- ITEM A: Describe the average volume of your tinnitus using a scale from 1 to 100
- ITEM B: What is the percentage of awake time in which tinnitus has been present in the last month? (1-100)
- ITEM C: What is the percentage of awake time in which tinnitus, in the last month, has made you unhappy and nervous?

Both control groups A and B were given the THI questionnaire. THI's total score was the value used to compare the results of manual therapy therapy with those of the standard therapy, TRT. TSCHQ, on the other hand, is a tool used in clinical trials, but is unfortunately not yet included in the TRT evaluation system; The patients in the control group B were therefore not given this questionnaire. To give more emphasis to any reduction in intensity, a factor not measured by THI, we will evaluate the results, including the modifications of the three numeric scales above.

Results

THI Total Score

Regarding Group A, the average value of T0 was 23.4 points. The average T1 stood at 16.4, outlining an average reduction of 7 points. The maximum value recorded at T0 was 60 points per 100 and the most significant decrease can be observed in clinical case 6, with a reduction of 16 points. In group B, however, the average T0 stands at 56.4 points, while T1 is around 25.33, with a substantial average reduction of 31.7 points. The maximum value at T0 was 90 points. Subject number 14

showed the biggest improvement, equal to 56 points difference.

The side diagram (fig 1) is relative to group A. The difference between T0 and T1 was statistically significant as a result of the two statistical tests performed (T-test; Wilcoxon test). The null hypothesis H0 would occur with ($\alpha = 0.050$).

Figure 1 Box plots for the THI Score of group A

Figure 2 Box plots for the THI Score of group B

Probation Level: ($p = 0.0088$)

Standard deviation T0: 17.02417

T1 standard deviation: 13.65609

The side-chart (fig 2) is relative to group B. The difference between T0 and T1 is also statistically significant, as demonstrated by specific tests (T-test, Wilcoxon test). The null hypothesis H0 would occur with ($\alpha = 0.050$).

Probation Level: ($p = 0.000721$)

Standard deviation T0: 20.85597

T1 standard deviation: 15.26278

TSCHQ Items

Figure 5 TSCHQ Items histogram for the patients the experimental group A

Figure4 TSCHQ variation from T0 to T1 for item A

This is the summary histogram of all sensitive items of TSCHQ, structured in numeric scales (1-100) of subjects in experimental group A.

The side chart refers to item A (fig 4). For this value, the average T0 was 44 points. At time T1 was 28 points, with an average reduction of 16 points per 100. This difference is to be considered statistically significant, as shown by the statistical tests performed (T-test; Wilcoxon test). The hypothesis H0 would occur with ($\alpha = 0,050$).

Probation Level: (p = 0.00557)
 Standard deviation T0: 21.70509
 T1 standard deviation: 18.73796

Figure3 TSCHQ variation from T0 to T1 for item B

The sidechart (fig 5), related to item B, shows us how, at T0, the average value was 77.5 points, against 53 of T1 time, with an average reduction of 24.5 points. This reduction would be statistically significant, as shown by the statistical tests performed (T-test; Wilcoxon test). The hypothesis H0 would occur with ($\alpha = 0,050$).

Probation Level: (p = 0.0124)
 Standard deviation T0: 36.22844
 T1 standard deviation: 22.63233

Figure 6 TSCHQ variation from T0 to T1 for item B

This last graph (fig 6), relating to item C, shows a T0 averaged at 32.2 points, while T1 was 18.7, with an average reduction of 13.5 points. This reduction would be statistically significant, as shown by the statistical tests performed (T-test; Wilcoxon test). The hypothesis H_0 would occur with ($\alpha = 0,050$).

Probation Level: ($p = 0.030516$)

Standard deviation T0: 30.61155

T1 standard deviation: 18.04347

Discussion

The response to the proposed treatments of both treatment groups was positive and encouraging. For control group B, the improvement was uniform, ie the benefit of the therapies was transversely present; All participants saw improvements in their initial condition, regardless of the starting situation and the tinnitus type that afflicted them. In experimental group A, which also showed a global improvements, it has come to outline a greater heterogeneity between results in individual patients, where some have reported a substantial improvement in both the perceived intensity and the influence on the quality of life, while others have found no benefit, at least as regards the reduction in intensity. The percentage of perceived consciousness in the last month and of the negative emotional reaction that at that time caused tinnitus aroused was in any case also diminished in the experimental group, in a rather homogeneous manner.

It is important to point out that the T0 situation in Group B is dramatically worse than the general situation in Group A. This gap is attributable to the fact that, for this study, the availability of patients was one of the major obstacles; there were also involved, therefore, subjects who, at least until then, did not consider their tinnitus a

problem. Group B patients, on the other hand, turned to the hospital as the last resort to face a problem they considered highly ingraining. The pool of users of the two groups was, therefore, very different.

TSCHQ item A is the most relevant value to be taken into account with regard to the experimental group of this study. In fact, the reduction in perceived intensity was the main target of myopathic therapies proposed, given the neuro-anatomy-physiological correlations described. Obviously, the modification of the intensity has also been able to influence positively the other evaluation parameters.

Conclusion

The eight neuromuscular therapy sessions have shown to be very effective, resulting in overall clinical improvement, both in terms of reduction in perceived intensity and for concomitant action on the limbic system: that is, a mood's tone improvement and a reduction in negative emotions related to tinnitus itself. The simultaneous reduction of items B and C, in fact, is interpreted as a substantial improvement in the quality of life.

Concerning the comparison between the two study groups, both proposed therapies were effective. As already shown, the type of use among them was, however, very different, since TRT did not introduce inclusion limits, while for the experimental group, subjects were subjected to a series of tests and examinations to establish a possible jointing of the musculoskeletal system in the genesis of tinnitus. In addition, the T0 situation of Group B subjects has always been much more severe than Group A.

The greatest difficulty encountered in this study, as in all other clinical trials related to tinnitus, remains to select a population sample that is both representative, of consistent size, and has as much as possible tinnitus equaletiopathogenesis. The limitations of this dissertation work are precisely these: the reduced number of participants, as well as the great heterogeneity of the treated patients. Neuromuscular manual therapy was, in fact, able to determine a very important improvement in some subjects, while being ineffective in others.

No remission has been achieved in any of the patients: this is due to the small number of sessions performed. The current bibliography recommends a period of treatment of not less than 3 months, while in this trial, the limit was set at approximately one month. In most patients, improvements were observed until the last session; This may suggest that continuing therapy for a longer period could have resulted in total resolution, at least in a couple of subjects.

Regarding this experience, it can be said that identifying and isolating a "pure" somatic tinnitus is not a simple thing: a certain degree of multifactoriality will

always be present, which, of course, complicates the management of tinnitus itself. What is very interesting is that even in subjects with more or less acute acoustic alterations, a certain degree of interaction with the perception of tinnitus has always been present. It is very difficult, however, to determine ahead how this interaction can lead to an improvement in the pathological condition of departure: what could have been expected has always been, at least in part, confused.

To conclude, it can now be assured with certainty that the figure of physiotherapist is of great importance in the management of tinnitus. Working in a team of experts that focus not on the disease, but on the patient in its entirety is and will always be the best choice for both people seeking help and for people who offer it.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.